

Butterflies in the the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë".

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Abstract

This study presents an overview of the butterfly fauna (Lepidoptera: Papilionoidea) in the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë", identifying 151 species across six families. Many are of ecological and conservation concern, with several listed as Vulnerable, Endangered, or Critically Endangered. Findings highlight the park's biodiversity value and call for urgent conservation actions.

Key words

Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea, biodiversity, National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë", conservation, endangered species, Red List.

Introduction

The Albanian Alps are a continuation of the Dinaric Mountains and extend to the north of Albania, to the west of Kosovo and to the south-east of Montenegro. These Alps extend to the valleys of the Ibri, covering a length of about 50 km. From an altitude of 500–600 m, they rise and reach over 2,000 m, being accompanied by the deep river valleys of Peja, Deçan and Erenik, with Drin as their southern border. The National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë" part of the Albania Alps, is one of the most important natural areas in Albania. It includes the highest peaks of the Albanian Alps, such as Maja e Jezercës, which reaches a height of 2,694 meters. The park is a habitat rich in biodiversity, including about 1,200 species of plants, many of which are endemic, and the animal world is rich and diverse, over 200 species of birds and 50 species of mammals, including many species of mammals, birds, reptiles and amphibians. In this ecosystem we can find large, protected and rare mammals such as lynx, wild goat, roe deer and bear. Also, in the fresh waters of the alpine rivers lives the otter, a species that faces global danger. The National Park of Albanian Alps is a protected area that was announced by the decision of the Council of Ministers no. 59, on January 26, 2022. This park includes the ecosystems known as "Valbona Valley" and "Theth Park", which have been declared as a national park (category II), as well as "Gashi Valley", which has the status of strict natural reserve (category I). In total, the Albanian Alps National Park covers an area of 82,844.65 hectares. The park's geology is characterized by various rock formations, such as limestone, that create spectacular landscapes with high cliffs and deep valleys. Different climates, from alpine to Mediterranean, contribute to a diverse ecosystem that supports the existence of a wide range of species. This makes this natural park an object of study for scientists and ecologists, offering opportunities for research in conservation biology and climate change, as well as promoting sustainable tourism and nature protection. Among the groups of fauna in the "Albanian Alps" National Park, Lepidoptera, or butterflies, constitute an important order of the class of Insects with an important impact on the park ecosystems. This park offers a diverse habitat with a different climate and landscape, which favours the diversity of insects in general and in particular of this order. Lepidoptera play an important role in the pollination of plants, helping in their reproduction and in the preservation of biodiversity. In addition to their ecological role, Lepidoptera are also indicators of environmental health. Their presence and their species composition can indicate changes in habitat and the impacts of climate change on biodiversity. The study of Lepidoptera in this park helps to monitor the ecosystem and provides valuable information for biodiversity management and conservation strategies. Thus, Lepidoptera contribute not only to the support of the ecosystem, but also to the preservation of nature in the Albanian Alps. The valorisation of the composition of Lepidoptera (Papilionidae) species in the "Albanian Alps" National Park is important for the preservation of the biodiversity and natural wealth of this ecosystem. The presence of these insects indicates a healthy and balanced ecosystem, and the identification of different species of this order helps to assess the environmental condition. A rich Lepidoptera biodiversity is a good indicator for habitat conservation and can help develop strategies for sustainable park management. In addition to their ecological role, butterflies have cultural and educational importance. These species offer opportunities for scientific research and environmental tourism activities, increasing interest in nature and caring for it. Education and awareness of the importance of butterflies can encourage visitors and local communities to engage in biodiversity conservation efforts. Thus, the valorisation of butterfly's species not only contributes to the preservation of the park's natural wealth, but also promotes a sustainable culture and respect for nature.

An overview of the Lepidoptera (Papilionoidea) of the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë"

From a detailed analysis of the study area based on the publication updated in 2023 - Butterflies of Albania by authors: Sylvain Cuvelier and Anila Paparisto <https://biodiversity.unitir.edu.al/index.html>, where a complete review of the Lepidoptera (Papilionoidea) fauna of Albania reported in the last 120 years is given (including here the complete list of publications about the Lepidoptera of Albania), in the area of interest shown in Fig. 1-2, it was estimated that 151 species of the order Lepidoptera, class Insecta belonging to 6 families have been historically reported for the area under study. A total of six butterfly families were recorded (Table 1): Papilionidae (5 species), Hesperidae (15 species), Pieridae (16 species), Lycaenidae (43 species), Riodinidae (1 species), and Nymphalidae (71 species). Among them, Nymphalidae had the highest number of species, while Riodinidae was the least represented with only one species.

Fig. 1. Location of the study area National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë", within Albania.

Fig. 2. Regional map of the Albanian Alps area showing the collection points (green dots) within the territory of the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë" during the September 2024 expedition (© Sylvain Cuvelier)

Of the 151 butterfly species historically recorded in the area, 13 species belonging to three families were collected during the expedition conducted from September 23 to 29, 2024. These include six species from the family Pieridae: *Colias alfacariensis* Ribbe, 1905, *Colias croceus* (Geoffroy, 1785), *Gonepteryx rhamni* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758); two species from the family Lycaenidae: *Lycaena phlaeas* (Linnaeus, 1761) and *Polyommatus icarus* (Rottemburg, 1775); and five species from the family Nymphalidae: *Aglais io* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Nymphalis antiopa* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Vanessa atalanta* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Lasiommata maera* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Lasiommata megera* (Linnaeus, 1767), as shown in detail in Table 3. Fig. 3 illustrates three distinct habitats within the study area of the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë".

Table 1. Species recorded from the National Park Alpet e Shqipërisë.
 Marked in green, species collected during the 2024 expedition.
 Marked in blue, species of ecological interest.

Nr	Family	Species	Status Albania Red List (2022)	Status Mediterranean Red List (2016)	Status European Red List (2010)	Hab. Directives Annex II, IV Bern Conv. 2 Cites II	Declining Disjunct N or S limit
1	Papilionidae	<i>Iphiclides podalirius</i>	LC	LC	LC		
2		<i>Papilio machaon</i>	LC	LC	LC		
3		<i>Parnassius apollo</i>	NT	LC	NT A2c	HD IV; B 2; C II	*
4		<i>Driopa mnemosyne</i>	NT	LC	NT A2c	HD IV; B 2	*
5		<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC	HD IV; B 2	*
6	Hesperiidae	<i>Hesperia comma</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
7		<i>Ochlodes sylvanus</i>	NE	LC	LC		
8		<i>Thymelicus acteon</i>	NT	LC	NT A2b		*
9		<i>Thymelicus lineola</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
10		<i>Thymelicus sylvestris</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
11		<i>Carterocephalus palaemon</i>	NE	NA	LC		*
12		<i>Carcharodus alceae</i>	LC	LC	LC		
13		<i>Muschampia floccifera</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		
14		<i>Erynnis tages</i>	LC	LC	LC		
15		<i>Pyrgus alveus</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
16	<i>Pyrgus andromedae</i>	NE	(not included)	LC		*	
17	<i>Pyrgus armoricanus</i>	LC	LC	LC			
18	<i>Pyrgus carthami</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
19	<i>Pyrgus malvae</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
20	<i>Spialai orbifer</i>	NE	LC	LC			
21	Pieridae	<i>Colias alfacariensis</i>	LC	LC	LC		
22		<i>Colias caucasica</i>	EN	EN B12ab (iii, iv)	LC		*
23		<i>Colias croceus</i>	NE	LC	LC		
24		<i>Gonepteryx rhamni</i>	NE	LC	LC		
25		<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i>	VU B1	LC	LC		*
26		<i>Leptidea juvernica</i>	DD	LC	LC (as L. reali)		*
27		<i>Leptidea sinapis</i>	NE	LC	LC		
28		<i>Anthocharis cardamines</i>	NE	LC	LC		
29		<i>Aporia crataegi</i>	NE	LC	LC		
30		<i>Pieris balcana</i>	LC	(not included)	LC		
31	<i>Pieris brassicae</i>	NE	LC	LC			
32	<i>Pieris ergane</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
33	<i>Pieris mannii</i>	NE	LC	LC			
34	<i>Pieris napi</i>	NE	LC	LC			
35	<i>Pieris rapae</i>	NE	LC	LC			
36	<i>Pontia edusa</i>	NE	LC	LC			
37	Lycaenidae	<i>Lycaena alciphron</i>	NE	LC	LC		
38		<i>Lycaena candens</i>	VU	(not included)	LC		
39		<i>Lycaena phlaeas</i>	NE	LC	LC		
40		<i>Lycaena thersamon</i>	NE	LC	LC		
41		<i>Lycaena tityrus</i>	NE	LC	LC		
42		<i>Lycaena virgaureae</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
43		<i>Aricia agestis</i>	NE	LC	LC		
44		<i>Aricia anteros</i>	LC	LC	NT A2c		
45		<i>Aricia artaxerxes</i>	NE	LC	LC		*
46		<i>Celastrina argiolus</i>	NE	LC	LC		
47	<i>Cupido argiades</i>	NE	LC	LC			
48	<i>Cupido minimus</i>	LC	LC	LC			
49	<i>Cupido osiris</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC			
50	<i>Cyaniris semiargus</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
51	<i>Eumedonia eumedon</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
52	<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i>	VU	LC	LC		*	
53	<i>Iolana iolas</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*	
54	<i>Kretania sephirus</i>	NE	LC (as P. pylaon)	LC		*	
55	<i>Lampides boeticus</i>	NE	LC	LC			
56	<i>Leptotes pirthous</i>	LC	LC	LC			
57	<i>Lysandra bellargus</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
58	<i>Lysandra coridon</i>	NE	LC	LC			
59	<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	VU D1D2	LC	LC		*	
60	<i>Phengaris arion</i>	CR	LC	EN A2bc	HD IV; B 2	*	
61	<i>Plebejus argus</i>	NE	LC	LC			
62	<i>Plebejus argyrognomon</i>	NE	LC	LC			
63	<i>Plenejus idas</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	
64	<i>Polyommatus amandus</i>	NE	LC	LC			
65	<i>Polyommatus damon</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*	
66	<i>Polyommatus daphnis</i>	NE	LC	LC			
67	<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i>	LC	LC	NT A2c			
68	<i>Polyommatus eros</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*	
69	<i>Polyommatus icarus</i>	NE	LC	LC			
70	<i>Polyommatus thersites</i>	NE	LC	LC		*	

71		<i>Pseudophilotes vicrama</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c	
72		<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
73		<i>Callophris rubi</i>	NE	LC	LC	
74		<i>Favonius quercus</i>	VU D1D2	LC	LC	
75		<i>Satyrium acaciae</i>	NE	LC	LC	
76		<i>Satyrium ilicis</i>	NE	LC	LC	
77		<i>Satyrium spini</i>	NE	LC	LC	
78		<i>Satyrium w-album</i>	VU A1b	LC	LC	*
79		<i>Thecla betulae</i>	VU A1b	LC	LC	*
80	Riodinidae	<i>Hamearis lucina</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC	*
81	Nymphalidae	<i>Apatura ilia</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
82		<i>Apatura iris</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
83		<i>Charaxes jasius</i>	LC	LC	LC	
84		<i>Argynnis pandora</i>	VU	LC	LC	
85		<i>Argynnis paphia</i>	NE	LC	LC	
86		<i>Boloria dia</i>	NE	LC	LC	
87		<i>Boloria euphrosyne</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
88		<i>Boloria graeca</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
89		<i>Boloria pales</i>	NE	(not included)	LC	*
90		<i>Boloria titania</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c	*
91		<i>Brenthis daphne</i>	NE	LC	LC	
92		<i>Brenthis hecate</i>	VU	LC	LC	
93		<i>Brenthis ino</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
94		<i>Fabriciana adippe</i>	NE	LC	LC	
95		<i>Fabriciana niobe</i>	LC	LC	LC	
96		<i>Issoria lathonia</i>	NE	LC	LC	
97		<i>Speyeria aglaja</i>	NE	LC	LC	
98		<i>Libythea celtis</i>	LC	LC	LC	
99		<i>Limenitis camilla</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
100		<i>Limenitis reducta</i>	LC	LC	LC	
101		<i>Aglais io</i>	NE	LC	LC	
102		<i>Aglais urticae</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
103		<i>Araschnia levana</i>	NE	NA	LC	*
104		<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i>	LC	LC	LC	HD II; B 2 *
105		<i>Euphydryas maturna</i>	DD	NA	VU A2c	II, IV; B 2 *
106		<i>Melitaea athalia</i>	LC	LC	LC	*
107		<i>Melitaea cinxia</i>	LC	LC	LC	
108		<i>Melitaea diamina</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
109		<i>Melitaea didyma</i>	NE	LC	LC	
110		<i>Melitaea phoebe</i>	LC	LC	LC	
111		<i>Melitaea trivia</i>	LC	LC	LC	
112		<i>Nymphalis antiopa</i>	LC	LC	LC	*
113		<i>Nymphalis polychloros</i>	LC	LC	LC	
114		<i>Polygonia c-album</i>	NE	LC	LC	
115		<i>Polygonia egea</i>	NE	LC	LC	
116		<i>Vanessa atalanta</i>	NE	LC	LC	
117		<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	NE	LC	LC	
118		<i>Brintesia circe</i>	LC	LC	LC	
119		<i>Chasara briseis</i>	LC	LC	NT A2c	*
120		<i>Coenonympha arcania</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
121		<i>Coenonympha orientalis</i>	VU	LC	VU A2c	*
122		<i>Coenonympha pamphilus</i>	NE	LC	LC	
123		<i>Coenonympha rhodopensis</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
124		<i>Erebia aethiops</i>	LC	NA	LC	*
125		<i>Erebia albertanus</i>	NE	(not included)	LC	*
126		<i>Erebia cassioides</i>	DD	LC	LC	*
127		<i>Erebia epiphron</i>	VU	LC	LC	*
128		<i>Erebia euryale</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
129		<i>Erebia gorge</i>	NT	LC	LC	*
130		<i>Erebia ligea</i>	NE	NA	LC	*
131		<i>Erebia medusa</i>	LC	LC	LC	*
132		<i>Erebia melas</i>	LC	LC	LC	*
133		<i>Erebia oeme</i>	LC	LC	LC	*
134		<i>Erebia ottomana</i>	NE	LC	LC	
135		<i>Erebia pandrose</i>	NT	(not included)	LC	*
136		<i>Erebia pronoe</i>	DD	(not included)	LC	*
137		<i>Erebia triarius</i>	DD	LC	LC	
138		<i>Hipparchia fagi</i>	LC	LC	NT	
139		<i>Hipparchia semele</i>	DD	LC	LC	*
140		<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c	*
141		<i>Hipparchia volgensis</i>	DD	LC	LC	*
142		<i>Hipparchia syriaca</i>	NE	LC	LC	*
143		<i>Hyponephele lycaon</i>	NE	LC	LC	
144		<i>Lasiommata maera</i>	NE	LC	LC	
145		<i>Lasiommata megera</i>	NE	LC	LC	*

146	<i>Lasiommata petropolitana</i>	NE	LC	LC
147	<i>Maniola jurtina</i>	NE	LC	LC
148	<i>Melanargia galathea</i>	NE	LC	LC
149	<i>Pararge aegeria</i>	NE	LC	LC
150	<i>Pyronia tithonus</i>	NE	LC	LC
151	<i>Satyrus ferula</i>	NE	LC	LC

Among the species recorded in the area from the literature (Table 1), 38 are of high ecological interest. These species are included in the Albanian Red List of Lepidoptera, revised by Cuvelier and Papparisto in 2023 and published online in [Fluturat e Shqipërisë](#). They belong to six families (Table 2). Several of these species are also of European conservation concern, as they are listed in the Habitats Directive Annexes II and IV, the Bern Convention (Bern Conv. 2), and CITES Appendix I (for further details, see Table 2).

Table 2. Species of high ecological interest in the study area

Nr	Family	Species	Status Albania Red List (2023)	Status Mediterranean Red List (2016)	Status European Red List (2010)	Hab. Directives Annex II, IV Bern Conv. 2 Cites II	Declining Disjunct N or S limit
1	Papilionidae	<i>Parnassius apollo</i>	NT	LC	NT A2c	HD IV; B 2; C II	*
2		<i>Driopa mnemosyne</i>	NT	LC	NT A2c	HD IV; B 2	*
3		<i>Zerynthia polyxena</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC	HD IV; B 2	*
4	Hesperiidae	<i>Thymelicus acteon</i>	NT	LC	NT A2b		*
5		<i>Muschampia floccifera</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		
6	Pieridae	<i>Colias caucasica</i>	EN	EN B12ab (iii, iv)	LC		*
7		<i>Leptidea duponcheli</i>	VU B1	LC	LC		*
8	Lycaenidae	<i>Lycaena candens</i>	VU	(not included)	LC		
9		<i>Cupido osiris</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC		
10		<i>Glaucopsyche alexis</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
11		<i>Iolana iolas</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*
12		<i>Phengaris alcon</i>	VU D1D2	LC	LC		*
13		<i>Phengaris arion</i>	CR	LC	EN A2bc	HD IV; B 2	*
14		<i>Polyommatus damon</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*
15		<i>Polyommatus dorylas</i>	LC	LC	NT A2c		
16		<i>Polyommatus eros</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*
17		<i>Pseudophilotes vicrama</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		
18		<i>Scolitantides orion</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
19		<i>Favonius quercus</i>	VU D1D2	LC	LC		
20		<i>Satyrrium w-album</i>	VU A1b	LC	LC		*
21		<i>Thecla betulae</i>	VU A1b	LC	LC		*
22	Riodinidae	<i>Hamearis lucina</i>	VU B2a	LC	LC		*
23	Nymphalidae	<i>Apatura ilia</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
24		<i>Apatura iris</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
25		<i>Argynnis pandora</i>	VU	LC	LC		
26		<i>Boloria titania</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*
27		<i>Brenthis hecate</i>	VU	LC	LC		
28		<i>Limenitis camilla</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
29		<i>Euphydryas aurinia</i>	LC	LC	LC	HD II; B 2	*
30		<i>Euphydryas maturna</i>	DD	NA	VU A2c	II, IV; B 2	*
31		<i>Melitaea diamina</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
32		<i>Chasara briseis</i>	LC	LC	NT A2c		*
33		<i>Coenonympha orientalis</i>	VU	LC	VU A2c		*
34		<i>Erebia epiphron</i>	VU	LC	LC		*
35		<i>Erebia gorge</i>	NT	LC	LC		*
36		<i>Erebia pandrose</i>	NT	(not included)	LC		*
37		<i>Hipparchia fagi</i>	LC	LC	NT		
38		<i>Hipparchia statilinus</i>	VU	LC	NT A2c		*

Referring to Table 2, four species of European conservation interest are identified: *Parnassius apollo* (Habitats Directive Annex IV; Bern Convention Appendix II; CITES Appendix II), *Driopa mnemosyne* (HD Annex IV; Bern II), *Zerynthia polyxena* (HD Annex IV; Bern II), and *Phengaris arion* (HD Annex IV; Bern II). The presence of these species underscores the ecological significance and biodiversity of the area, indicating that it harbors unique habitats critical for their survival. Protecting these habitats not only supports the conservation of these priority species but also contributes to broader efforts to preserve the region's natural heritage, promoting ecological stability and resilience.

Based on the analysis of the Red List of European Butterflies (Table 2), 13 species found in the study area are classified as Near Threatened (NT), under categories A2c and A2b. These species include: *Parnassius apollo*, *Driopa mnemosyne*, *Thymelicus acteon*, *Muschampia floccifera*, *Iolana iolas*, *Polyommatus damon*, *Polyommatus dorylas*, *Polyommatus eros*, *Pseudophilotes vicrama*, *Boloria titania*, *Chasara briseis*, *Hipparchia fagi*, and *Hipparchia statilinus*.

Two additional species recorded in this area are classified as Vulnerable (VU A2c) according to the IUCN Red List. These species are *Euphydryas maturna* and *Coenonympha orientalis*.

The species *Phengaris arion* is classified as Endangered (EN A2bc) according to the IUCN Red List.

The identification of 13 Near Threatened species, including emblematic butterflies such as *Parnassius apollo* and *Driopa mnemosyne*, highlights the ecological importance of the study area.

Their presence indicates a habitat that supports rich biodiversity but also faces environmental pressures, underscoring the need for proactive conservation measures. Furthermore, the occurrence of two Vulnerable species (*Euphydryas maturna* and *Coenonympha orientalis*) and one Endangered species (*Phengaris arion*) emphasizes the urgency for targeted conservation strategies to safeguard these populations and preserve the ecological integrity of the region.

Overall, these findings underscore the rich biodiversity of the area and the vital importance of preserving its natural habitats for future generations. Based on the detailed analysis of the 2023 Albanian Red List of Butterflies, five species occurring in the area are classified as Near Threatened (NT): *Parnassius apollo*, *Driopa mnemosyne*, *Thymelicus acteon*, *Erebia gorge*, and *Erebia pandrose*. Their presence signals the ecological sensitivity of the region and the need for focused conservation efforts to prevent further decline.

Fig. 3. Collection stations in order from left to right: Lake Sylbica; The dry stream, on the way to the Peja pass; the path of Peja's neck.

While 26 butterfly species, also according to the 2023 classification <https://biodiversity.univ.it.edu.al/>, are classified in the vulnerable category (VU) as follows: *Zerynthia polyxena* VU B2a; *Muschampia floccifera* VU; *Leptidea duponcheli* VU B1; *Lycaena candens* VU; *Cupido osiris* VU B2a; *Glaucopteryx alexis* VU; *Iolana iolas* VU; *Phengaris alcon* VU D1D2; *Polyommatus damon* VU; *Polyommatus eros* VU; *Pseudophilotes vicrama* VU; *Scolitantides orion* VU; *Favonius quercus* VU D1D2; *Satyrion w-album* VU A1b; *Thecla betulae* VU A1b; *Hamearis lucina* VU B2a; *Apatura ilia* VU; *Apatura iris* VU; *Argynnis pandora* VU; *Boloria titania* VU; *Brenthis hecate* VU; *Limenitis camilla* VU; *Melitaea diamina* VU; *Coenonympha orientalis* VU; *Erebia epiphron* VU; *Hipparchia statilinus* VU.

In the list of endangered Albanian butterflies, among 38 endangered species according to IUCN criteria, for this area, there is 1 species *Colias caucasica* classified in the "endangered" category EN and 1 species *Phengaris arion*, classified as "critically endangered" CR.

In the list of endangered Albanian butterflies, among 38 endangered species according to IUCN criteria, for this area, there is 1 species *Colias caucasica* classified in the "endangered" category EN and 1 species *Phengaris arion*, classified as "critically endangered" CR.

Among the species presented in Table 2, from our annual monitoring in the field, 29 species of them show signs of decline in their populations, this decline, if evidenced, is presented for each species in Table no. 2 with the symbol "*".

The presence of 26 *Vulnerable* butterfly species, alongside one *Endangered* species and one *Critically Endangered* species in the area, underscores the urgent need for conservation efforts to address declining populations. The annual monitoring revealing a decline in 29 species highlights the pressing challenges these butterflies face, emphasizing the importance of targeted strategies to protect their habitats and ensure their survival. This data not only reflects the ecological richness of the area but also serves as a call to action for effective conservation measures to safeguard these critical species for the future.

Conclusion

The expeditions carried out in the "Albanian Alps" National Park, from September 23 to 29, 2024 offer an important insight into the diversity of Lepidoptera in this protected area. From the analyses carried out, it results that 151 species of the Lepidoptera order have been reported so far, with a diverse representation of species and different families. During the expedition, 13 species were collected despite the time that does not coincide with the season when Lepidoptera (Papilionoidea) have their maximum activity, due to the temperature and altitude of the area. Historical and updated data prove the importance of this park as an important habitat for these insects. The presence of species of ecological interest, some of which are classified as endangered at the European level and are also included in the Habitats Directive and the Bern Convention, shows the need for immediate measures to protect and preserve biodiversity in this area.

In addition to ecological importance, Lepidoptera (Papilionoidea) also provide opportunities for scientific and educational research, promoting awareness of nature conservation. Increasing interest in Lepidoptera as indicators of environmental health can help improve strategies for sustainable park management. However, it is important that the monitoring and study of these species continue systematically to ensure the protection of biodiversity and the preservation of the ecosystems of the Albanian Alps. This will contribute to the development of sustainable tourism and the promotion of the natural values of this exceptional park.

Recommendations for the Revival of the National Park Albanian Alps

- **Biodiversity Monitoring:** Implement a regular monitoring program for *Lepidoptera* and other key species within the park to track changes in biodiversity over time and inform effective conservation and management strategies.
- **Further Studies:** Promote scientific research aimed at identifying and documenting new species, as well as those of particular ecological interest. Priority should be given to studies on the ecology and behavior of *Lepidoptera* and other ecologically important species within the territory of the Albanian Alps National Park.
- **Education and Awareness:** Develop educational activities for visitors and local communities to raise awareness about the importance of *Lepidoptera* and overall biodiversity. These may include workshops, guided excursions, and exhibitions organized within the park.
- **Promotion of Sustainable Tourism:** Create tourist itineraries within the park that include opportunities for observing *Lepidoptera* and other wildlife, aiming to foster greater interest in nature and promote its conservation.
- **Habitat Protection:** Implement measures to preserve natural habitats by preventing their degradation through the sustainable management of natural resources.
- **Collaboration with Experts:** Foster cooperation among scientists, environmentalists, and local authorities within the park area to develop and implement effective strategies for biodiversity conservation.
- **Creation of Conservation Units:** Establish volunteer and community groups to actively contribute to biodiversity conservation and protection, while raising awareness about the ecological importance of the National Park "Alpet e Shqipërisë".
- **Policy and Legislation:** Review and reinforce biodiversity protection policies and legislation to ensure they are robust, effective, and enforceable in practice.
- **Increasing Management Capacities:** Provide training for park staff and local communities in biodiversity management and conservation, incorporating new techniques and sustainable practices.

Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally to the conception, analysis, and writing of this work. Each author was involved in all stages of the research process, from conceptualization through data analysis, to drafting and revising the manuscript.

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Supplementary material

[S1](#). List of species collected during the September 2024 expedition and the coordinates of the collection points.

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